

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF ALGORITHM OF CONCEPTS' STUDY IN MODERN BRITISH POLITICAL TEXTS

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Abstract

Text analysis constitutes an important part of the academic plan in the preparation of senior students of English language departments, as the skills of such analysis enable them to comprehend all possible plots of a text and thus to understand it to the full. It is certainly important that the most popular and representative text genres be within the study material. Being one of the bulkiest volumes of publicistic matter, texts on political issues, in particular, interviews of famous British politicians are logically included into the material for studying. Hence, teaching adequate and full understanding of political texts constitutes one of the major tasks in teaching analytical reading and generally in students' preparation; this factor demonstrating the value of algorithms in the process of analysis of these texts. Given the reasons mentioned, the topicality of the suggested paper is clear, and its objectives can be worded as the development and shaping of the algorithm which can be used by senior students in their work at the analysis of a political text and pointing out the main concepts of the current political discourse. The material of the paper is interviews of famous British politicians of the 21 century.

Keywords: algorithm, political discourse, political interview, conceptual analysis, concept.

Introduction

Articles on modern political topics have always been included into studying material in the programs for preparation language specialists. So, the algorithm of analyzing such texts is quite important for teaching senior students to adequately comprehend them; this demonstrates the value and topicality of correct algorithm in the process of analysis of contemporary British texts of interviews of famous British politicians. The paper is aimed at the development and shaping of the algorithm which can be used by senior students in their work at the analysis of a political text and pointing out the main concepts of political texts which are treated as an integral component of the political discourse. The material of the research is interviews of prominent British political figures of the 21st century. The algorithm includes a number of stages during which the most important and frequently actualized concepts are singled out and the language means of their verbalization are studied. The research shows that the suggested algorithm facilitated the students' deeper understanding of political texts and improved their linguistic analytical skills, thus influencing positively their language competence. That is why the given methodology of work with texts of political character can be recommended for wider implementation in the preparation of students of foreign languages departments of universities.

Methodology

In cognitive linguistics the following methods of research of verbalized concepts are singled out: the description of the associative field of the concept; the

analysis of the definitions; the etymological analysis; the method of concept study through the lexical-grammatical field of lexemes which represent the concept (14); the associative experiment, the analysis of verbalization in individual author's nominations, cognitive-semantic analysis (15; 18), concepts' comparative analysis in different cultures, comparison of individual-author's and national concepts, the conceptual analysis.

Main part

To reveal the essence of the modern understanding of cognitive analysis, it's necessary to dwell upon its definitions. The Ukrainian linguist O. Selivanova defines conceptual analysis as the main method of logical analysis of the language and cognitive linguistics, which involves modeling and description of concepts (17, p. 262). According to the researcher, the goal of this analysis is the reconstruction of cognitive mechanisms of individual or collective consciousness, which mediate the formation and organization of knowledge about the objects of reality and the results of internal reflexive experience.

According to professor A. Martynuk, the conceptual analysis consists of two aspects: logical and eidetic. The logical aspect is aimed at establishing regularities within the organization of the concept, identifying its elements and establishing connections between them. The eidetic aspect is aimed to establish how a holistic concept exists in mind (11, p. 47). One of the main goals of conceptual analysis is the construction of a conceptual model of that informational element that is represented by a sign (12). To achieve this, the elements

of meaning must be grouped in a special way, ordered and interrelated. Such conceptual structures as propositions, frames, scenarios, prototype models etc. are used for the task mentioned. Here it is worth mentioning the theory of metaphor and metonymy by G. Lakoff and M. Johnson, the conception of prototype theory of E. Rosh and G. Lakoff, frame semantics of Ch. Fillmore. These cognitive models provide the development and saving information about the world in individual's mind.

While modeling the structure of a concept, it is important not only to divide the means of verbalization into lexical-semantic groups, but also to establish relations between semantic classes of parts of nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs, to establish connections with the semantic core of the concept (23).

Scholars claim that to analyze is to explicate. The verb "to explicate" means either to explain empirically or to provide an analysis of a concept (22).

From the point of view of St. Petrina, conceptual analysis is a means of clarifying or explicating and giving definition, dimension, and meaning to ordinary and obscure expressions (i.e., cultural, natural, of spiritual things, image, text, sound, etc.) (21, p. 1).

Conceptual analysis of discourse phenomena constitutes a widely-spread and captivating area of linguistic research. And among numerous discourse studies of the last decades, political discourse (hereinafter PD) proves to be, probably, one of the most popular and interesting fields. Some scholars claim that the growing interest to the study of political texts can be explained by the following factors: a) the inside requirements of linguistic theory, which at various times directed its attention to various spheres of the language system functioning; b) politological issues of political thinking and its links with political behavior, and also by the need in development of the methods of analysis of political texts; c) by the social request, the ambition for setting political communication free from manipulating public consciousness (6, p. 245).

Political discourse is always related to the issue of power at different levels. The fact that the consciousness of large groups of people is being manipulated through PD remains indisputable. The language picture of the political world of Great Britain is a complex formation of mental units (concepts, guidelines, myths, values, etc.) related to the political sphere of communication and PR. Concepts play an important role in shaping the image of the world, both for an individual and for society (3).

Perception, categorization and conceptualization of the surrounding reality by a linguistic individual begins with the understanding of the phenomena of the surrounding world, the objects organized in it, and with the determination of the place of a person in the system of these objects. The result of such processes is the emergence of concepts (5, p. 606 – 622.).

In the "Big Dictionary of the Modern Ukrainian Language" (2003), edited by V. Busel, the concept is explained as "formulation, general concept, opinion" (1).

In his "Principles of Psychology" W. James writes that the concept is a component of the conception: "The

function by which we defined a relatively clear and permanent subject of discourse is called a concept; and the thoughts that embody it are called concepts. But the word *concept* is often used as an object of the discourse itself" (8).

According to the point of view of a famous Ukrainian linguist I. Shevchenko, speech functioning of concepts depends on the context. Out of context, the word has only the lexical-conceptual meaning reflected in the dictionary. Therefore, cognitive research is discursive in its paradigmatic essence, in contrast to the semantic study of lexical units. When constructing the world, the speaker uses all his linguistic and social experience, knowledge, and interpretive mechanisms. This experience determines the constitutive categories of discourse, and also manifests itself in the processes of language categorization and understanding of reality (19, p. 9 – 20.).

The issue of the typology of PD genres remains still unresolved, although in the conditions of the rapid development of Internet mass media, the polyfunctionality and multigenre nature of political communication requires clarification of the dialogic and monologic characteristics of speech interaction. The interpretation of a political interview as a speech genre of PD involves taking into account its textual features, both in political and mass media communication. The political interview is one of the most effective and oldest methods of presenting information.

There is no universal definition for the "political interview". The political interview is a means of representing the image of a politician and a means of communicating relevant information on behalf of a specific politician (13). In the Journalist's Dictionary, an interview (from the English interview – literally a meeting, conversation) is defined as a genre of journalism, a journalist's conversation with a well-known or simply knowledgeable person, mainly on an important topic, intended for publication in the mass media (9). The political interview belongs to political speech genres along with the statement and the message. The political interview has a dialogic character and is a verbal representation of a conversation between a journalist and a politician. Thematically, the political interview highlights the problems of political life, and by function it is intended to present relevant information about certain events and the characteristics of these events by a political subject on their own behalf (10, pp. 187-191).

The peculiarities of a political interview are its mediated nature, namely: the politician gives answers, but does not always remove the uncertainty of the question, and says exactly what the journalist requires. In most cases, the addressee politician presents his own position and creates his own positive image, rather than giving a direct answer to the journalist's question. It is by definition an interview in which the people interviewed are "members of the political elite – i.e. political decisionmakers who hold, or actively seek to hold widely publicised public offices" (2, p.133). Blum-Kulka describes political interviews as "highly structured speech events" with at least two main characteristics. The first characteristic refers to the asymmetrical character of the relation between the interviewer and

the interviewee stressing that only the interviewer is in the position to ask questions. As a rule one could say that rhetorical questions are the only questions posed by politicians (2, p.133). The second main feature of the political interview is the existence of “a well-established set of implicit norms which govern the verbal behavior of interactants in relating to each other during the interview” (4). The interviewer usually addresses the politician in a very respectful way by his or her title or family name whereas the politicians typically do not address the interviewers at all (16).

Findings.

Each country at a certain time of its development is characterized by events and changes that determine the main concepts of PD. In the process of studying the research material as related to this study, *an algorithm* for analyzing the concepts of British political interviews was developed. The *algorithm* can be used for senior students training, at the practical classes of analytical reading. This *algorithm* includes the following stages:

- determining the main topic/topics of the British political interview;
- taking into account the changes that are happening or may happen in the country in connection with this event;
- selection of concepts that are semantically related to this topic/topics;
- definition of lexical units that are verbalizers of the concepts of a certain political interview.
- Let's consider the actualization of concepts using the example of an interview with one of the former prime ministers of Great Britain, Theresa May.
- The main topic of this interview is Brexit. When Brexit is in the focus of attention, one needs to have an idea of the main changes that are happening or may happen in the country in connection with this event:
 - elections to determine the legality of Brexit;
 - social protection of the population;
 - immigration;
 - economic relations with the EU.

PD researches of previous years prove that the main concept of political discourse is the concept of POWER (22; 23), so it is logical that it is actualized in all political interviews. The research material shows that this basic concept is often actualized with the help of more specific concepts that denote persons and institutions that are embodiments of power, for example: *GOVERNMENT, PRIME MINISTER, [HEALTH] SECRETARY*. Let's show it in the fragments of the interview:

1) *THERESA MAY: Right, well there are lots of challenges in our politics at the moment, there are lots of challenges that the government face ...*

(...)

2) *THERESA MAY: I'm delivering what I believe the British people want their government to deliver and I think it's not just an issue about Brexit itself but it is actually an issue to me about trust in politicians that if we ...*

Here the concept POWER is verbalized by the nouns government, politics and politicians. Also, in this

fragment, the concept TRUST is actualized with the corresponding name of this concept.

In the following example, the actualization of the POWER concept is observed by the noun phrase *the desire of other parties* and *the will of the British people*.

3) *THERESA MAY: And what became clear as we were looking through those negotiations, started those negotiations, started the process of triggering them, what became clear, increasingly clear, as is clear in this election campaign, is the desire of other parties to frustrate the will of the British people. That's why I thought it was right to go out for an election.*

Due to the fact that the purpose of a political interview is to highlight the point of view of a political figure on certain issues of state or public importance, the concept *OPINION* is always observed in a political interview. The analysis of the actual material shows that the named concept is genre-defying for the political interview genre. In each interview, there is a journalist and a public figure, so the point of view of both the journalist and the public figure can be expressed. In the analyzed fragment of Theresa May's interview, multiple expressions of the concept *OPINION* can be observed, and the speech expressions of this concept can be different, that is, belong to different morphological classes of lexical units.

In the analyzed fragment of Theresa May's interview, there is a multiple expression of the concept *OPINION*, and the speech exponents of this concept can be different, i.e. belong to different morphological classes of lexical units:

4) *JEREMY PAXMAN: Theresa May, when did you realise that you'd got the wrong answer to the biggest question of our times in politics?*

THERESA MAY: Well I am tempted to ask you, Jeremy, what you think, do you mean you are talking about Brexit?

JP: Well of course.

(...)

JP: What was it that convinced you that Brexit was so bad for Britain?

THERESA MAY: I set out my reasons for deciding that we should on balance stay within the European Union, I voted to remain, I campaigned to remain and...

The verbal expressions of the *OPINION* concept are verbs and verb phrases *immigration* та *immigrants*:

5) *JP: Immigration was your main task, to get it down to what you promised in the manifesto which was 100,000 or less non-EU immigrants per year net. You didn't do that did you?*

THERESA MAY: Net migration, no, we didn't achieve that. What happened ...

(...)

THERESA MAY: Yes, Jeremy I'm not sitting here saying it wasn't, I'm accepting that what we had to do was to ensure that we were rooting out abuse in the system but there is no single moment where you take one measure which changes the immigration figures. It is a constant work to ensure that you are dealing with immigration and ensuring there is no more abuse in the system. There is more work to be done. We will of

course have another tool to do this when we leave the European Union because we'll be able to introduce rules for people coming from within the European Union but this will be a constant work.

One of the actualized concepts of this interview is the concept *PEOPLE*, expressed by the verb phrases *to take people's views, we gave people the choice, respecting the will of the people* and, *decided to leave the European Union* and the plural noun *people* and the noun phrase *the British people*, as in the following fragments:

(6) *THERESA MAY: And I also said that the sky wouldn't fall in if we left the European Union, we gave people the choice ...*

JP: So you changed your mind then, you changed your mind.

THERESA MAY: I'll answer that, we gave people the choice, Jeremy and the British people decided to leave the European Union and I think it's important for them to see their politicians delivering on that choice and respecting the will of the people (...)

In this example the use of the verb phrase *you changed your mind* as a speech expression of the concept *OPINION* in the journalist's speech take place.

Since the topic of the chosen interview is Brexit, the question of the successful exit of Great Britain from the European Union is one of the leitmotifs of this interview. Therefore, it is worth considering the speech implementation of the *SUCCESS* concept as one of the more frequent interview concepts. It is represented by such expressions as *success of Brexit, to make a success*:

7) *THERESA MAY: I take the view that we can make a success of Brexit. (приклад вираження концепції success) I take the view that the British people want us to make that success.*

JP: But you don't believe in it.

THERESA MAY: Of course, Jeremy, as Prime Minister I've been out there already ensuring that the negotiations are going to start and I want to ensure there is a strong hand in those negotiations. I believe in making a success of Brexit for the whole of the United Kingdom.

JP: But you don't really believe in it do you?

THERESA MAY: I believe in making a success of Brexit.

In the following example, three concepts, *OPINION*, *BREXIT* and *SUCCESS*, are updated simultaneously. The concept *OPINION* is expressed by the phrase *the view of the British people, I think, I genuinely think, I believe*. The concept *SUCCESS* is realized by the name of the concept and the verbal combination with it. The verbal expression of the *BREXIT* concept is the corresponding name of the concept and verb phrases with it: *get Brexit right, making a success of Brexit*.

(8) *THERESA MAY: No, the referendum drew a line under those debates, what the referendum did was took the view of the British people. Now I think it's right that we do that now and I think, I genuinely think that if we get Brexit right – and this is really important for us – if we get Brexit right we can make a real success of the opportunities that open up for us*

but we can only do that if we grasp those opportunities and I believe ...

JP: You still think it's a bad idea.

THERESA MAY: No, I believe we're doing the right thing in making a success of Brexit.

JP: Well of course you want to make a success of it ...

Summarizing the analysis of this interview, the following can be stated:

- the main notions in the interview, represented by the corresponding concepts, are *POWER*, *OPINION*, *PEOPLE*, *BREXIT*, *IMMIGRATION* and *SUCCESS*, characterized by different frequency of use;
- the *OPINION* concept has the highest frequency of implementation; it can be called the genre-forming concept of this interview;
- most of the named concepts are realized by words of different morphological classes;
- selected concepts are often implemented using the corresponding names of the concepts, as well as their synonyms;
- several concepts are realized in one speech of a speaker-politician.

It is interesting to analyze the speech implementation of the concepts in the interview of Gordon Brown (2020), the topic of which is stated in the preface. These topics are:

- economic crisis;
- retreat from globalization;
- priority fight against Covid-19.

In the interview of the former Prime Minister of Great Britain, the concepts with the corresponding names

CRISIS, *GLOBALIZATION/DEGLOBALIZATION*, *CORONAVIRUS* were vividly verbalized. Since this is a political interview, the concepts *POWER*, *OPINION*, and *ACTION* are often used.

In the following fragment, the verbalization of several concepts is observed. The *GLOBALIZATION/DEGLOBALIZATION* concept is expressed by the proper name *deglobalisation* and the noun phrase *crisis of globalisation*. The concept *CRISIS* is expressed by the noun phrases *global crisis* and *crisis of globalization*. The concept *OPINION* is verbalized by the verb expressions *I think, to make a distinction* and *to rethink what we mean*. There is also a *NATION* concept expressed by the phrase *global society*:

(9) *New Statesman: Is this the beginning of "deglobalisation" – or a temporary blip?*

Gordon Brown: People have tried to make a distinction between a global crisis and a crisis of globalisation. It is undoubtedly a crisis of globalisation. Whether it's the beginning of the end of the global supply chains, the global flows of capital, the global communications I doubt, but I think it's going to force us to rethink what we mean by the management of the global economy. It's going to force us to rethink what constitutes the right policies for a global society.

In the analyzed interview of Gordon Brown, cases of verbalization of several concepts are repeatedly observed. Let's consider these examples in more detail:

(10) **GB**: Some of the assumptions of **globalisation** are being challenged, but it actually makes it more important that we put the case for **global cooperation** rather than simply accept that certain countries are resistant to it. If you've got a medical emergency, a **pandemic**, it is the most obvious example of where countries have to cooperate. You cannot solve this problem in one country; it has got to be solved in every country.

(...)

You've got what people now call "vaccine nationalism". You've got this idea that countries just take what they want in a race to the bottom in a global search for equipment. The only way **to solve some of these problems** is to **cooperate to build up capacity**, to search together for a vaccine and a cure, to stop a second and third round by protecting the poorest countries, from whom the disease would flow back into the West if we did nothing. When we talk about self-isolation, **we've got to think** that national self-isolation has become an issue, but we've got to fight it.

NS: As chancellor you were a leading advocate for debt cancellation. Rwanda's president, Paul Kagame, said this week that **he thinks** Africa is going to need at least \$100bn to ensure continuation. The whole of the world is taking on huge debts to fight **Covid-19**. Is debt relief going to have to be a broader solution?

The concepts of **GLOBALIZATION**, **ACTION**, **CORONAVIRUS** and **OPINION** are verbalized here. The **GLOBALIZATION** concept is implemented by the corresponding name of this concept. The concept of **ACTION** is verbalized by the noun phrase **global cooperation** and the verb phrases **to solve some of these problems, to cooperate to build up capacity**. The concept **CORONAVIRUS** is realized by the nouns **pandemic** and **Covid-19**. The concept of **OPINION** is actualized by the verb expressions **we've got to think, he thinks**.

11) **GB** Debt relief for the poorest countries is the starting point because it releases money very quickly. If you can tell **people** today that they don't have to make debt interest payments for the rest of the year, and hopefully for the rest of the next year, then that is money that can be used for health and for social safety nets. At the moment, as I understand it, sub-Saharan Africa is paying more in debt interest payments than it is investing in health. If you can give **people** the assurance that they won't be called on to pay debt interest payments, they can begin to spend that money on what is urgently needed.

I think, however, it's not just debt relief. The **IMF** and the World Bank have got to **open up the resources**. There seems to be a mismatch between what we say we need to do at a national level in Britain, the US and the rest of Europe, and what we seem to be willing to do on a global level.

(...)

You could find a way that it was delivered and managed to help the poorest countries. And then the **IMF** and the World Bank – one of the reasons that we were able to underpin the world economy [in the **financial crisis** in 2009] is that **we increased the resources**

they were able to give to poorer countries. **I would have thought** that the \$100bn that President Kagame mentions is an understatement of what's going to be needed.

In this example, we also observe a combination of several concepts at once. The concept **NATION** is expressed by the noun **people**; the concept **OPINION** is verbalized by verb expressions **I think, I would have thought**; verbal expressions of the **ACTION** concept are verb phrases **open up the resources, we increased the resources**; the **CRISIS** concept is actualized by the noun phrase **financial crisis**.

In the next fragment of the interview, the speech implementation of the eight concepts is noted.

(12) **GB**: The problem is we've got a mismatch between the need for this global cooperation, the willingness to undertake it on the part of leaders, and the capacity of these institutions to **deal with the problem**. **I think** we're finding that some of the reasons **people are hostile to globalisation** – or global cooperation, I should say – is because they don't feel the institutions have been sufficiently effective. But the answer, of course, is to **give them the leadership** that's necessary.

NS: The by-product of the fight against **Covid-19** is a recession far deeper than the global **financial crisis** of 2008-09. During that slowdown in the UK, **poverty continued to fall** because of tax credits and other interventions. **Do you think** the time is now right for, say, a universal basic income? Or **do you think** the traditional methods of a strong welfare state are better equipped to deal with the problem?

GB I think this crisis throws up the whole question of what is the social contract moving forward. That's true in Britain, but it's true in every other Western country where there is some kind of social contract. **I think** that there are four things the social contract should do.

(...)

The one most obvious feature of this **crisis** is that children in particular, despite all the measures that the **government** has introduced, are losing out very, very badly. You will see rates of **child poverty** rise substantially over the next few months and years as a result of the decisions that the **government** has taken that provide some sort of support for employment, some sort of rise in Universal Credit, but nothing that is properly directed towards the biggest **poverty problem** that this country and many other countries face: **rising poverty among children**.

Here the concept **ACTION** is realized by the expressions **deal with the problem, give them the leadership, to deal with**; the **OPINION** concept is realized by the verb-verbal expressions **I think, Do you think** and the adjectival expression **different view**; the **NATION** concept is realized by verb expressions **people are hostile, people are not able to work, people somehow believed, people take**; the **GLOBALIZATION** concept is implemented by the corresponding name of this concept. The concept **CORONAVIRUS** is verbalized by the noun **Covid-19**; the concept **CRISIS** is expressed by the corresponding name of this concept, the noun expression **financial crisis** and the verb expression **crisis**

throws up; the concept *POVERTY* is realized by repeated repetition of the corresponding name of this concept in verb expressions *poverty continued to fall, child poverty, poverty problem, rising poverty among children*); the *POWER* concept is realized by the nouns *government, Conservatives* and the verb expression *government steps in*.

The analysis shows that the observations regarding the implementation of concepts in the previous interview are valid for this interview as well, but the topics of this interview determine the specifics of the use of concepts in it. The *POWER* and *OPINION* concepts are also implemented here.

Thus, the suggested examples demonstrate quite well that the process of singling out the concepts of political texts, as well as the linguistic ways of their verbalization, with the use of the suggested algorithm facilitate the senior students' adequate understanding of political texts in question and their involvement into the set of problems of the British PD on the whole.

It is of interest to study the system of concepts verbalized in a finished political text, as it enables to have a full picture of ideas expressed there together with their frequency. This helps a reader (senior students, in our case) to grasp the most important notions and to analyze the ways these notions are expressed in modern British PD. From this angle the interview with the former Prime Minister of Great Britain Boris Johnson (2022) can serve an example. The title of the interview is "In full: Exclusive with Boris Johnson on the Ukraine conflict". The topics of the interview are:

- the war with Russia;
- the war of Independence;
- Britain's military and economic support to Ukraine;

- the use of nuclear weapons;
- democracy and freedom.

Our analysis showed that the concepts verbalized in the interview are characterized by the following frequency of their manifestation: *THE WAR IN UKRAINE* – 35 (number of usage); *SUPPORT* – 21; *OPINION* – 20; *NUCLEAR WEAPONS* – 14; *THE WAR OF INDEPENDENCE* – 7; *DEMOCRACY* – 6; *FREEDOM* – 5. It is illustrative enough to show and analyze the use of some of them, as it testifies to the seriousness and determination of the interviewed person. In this interview the key concepts are *THE WAR IN UKRAINE* and *SUPPORT*. For instance:

(13) *Mark Austin: Boris Johnson, Vladimir Putin thought that this war would be over in days in a week or so yeah did you fear the same?*

Boris Johnson: That was certainly the advice that we were getting and the some of the defense intelligence people were saying, look this is going to be wery, very one-sided. The Russians are just going to roll through and numerically they're so strong and they're so well, so we're equipped. I'd been to Ukraine a few times before and I kind of knew that they were going to fight, and if you you've been there a lot and you talked to people who've fought in the East in, in Donbass since 2014. These are hardened, hardened fighters, so I thought it would be much tougher than, than Putin thought.

In this part of the interview the concept *WAR IN UKRAINE* is implemented through the nouns *war, the Russians*. The verbal phrase *they (Ukrainians) were going to fight*, the adverbial phrase *in the East in, in Donbass since 2014*, the noun phrase with the repeated adjective *hardened, hardened fighter*, and the noun phrase *it would be much tougher than, than Putin thought* characterize Boris Johnson's positive attitude to the Ukrainian soldiers and confidence in their military strength, thus being the supportive but emotionally charged way to verbalise the concept *OPINION*.

The depicted algorithm of work with political texts at analytical reading classes (senior students) was used in practical work and in the work at diploma thesis in 2019-2020, 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 academic years. It was evident that the suggested algorithm facilitated the students' better and deeper understanding of political texts and improved their linguistic analytical skills, thus improving their language competence. That is why the given methodology of work with texts of political character can be recommended for wider implementation in the students' preparation in the field of the English language. Besides, this work increases the interest of young people to texts of political character and to reading British newspapers and magazines, broadening in such a way their general knowledge and social and political awareness.

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